

WINTER PHOTO REGISTRATION OF THE GOLDEN EAGLE (*AQUILA CHRYSAETOS*) IN THE WESTERN PART OF TRANSCARPATHIA

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Зимова фотофіксація беркута (*Aquila chrysaetos*) в західному Закарпатті. - Л. Потіш. - Беркут. 33 (1-2). 2024. - Беркут вважається рідкісним видом Закарпатської області, зустрічали його переважно у східній частині. Використання фотопасток дало змогу зафіксувати цей вид у басейні р. Люта (48° 48' 15'' N, 22° 35' 18'' E) в лютому 2024 р. Птах мав голубе кільце на правій лапі. За даними словацьких колег, він був закільцьований ними 3–4 роки тому.

Ключові слова: Закарпатська область, фауна, поширення, кільцювання.

Abstract. Golden Eagle is a species with a small number, occurred mainly in eastern part of Transcarpathian region. Using camera trap the first observation of this species in Lyuta river basin (48° 48' 15'' N, 22° 35' 18'' E) was from February 18, 2024. The blue ring on the right foot was installed by Slovak colleagues 3–4 years ago.

Key words: Transcarpathian region, fauna, distribution, ringing.

For the bird fauna of Transcarpathian region, the Golden Eagle is a species with a small number, occurred mainly in its eastern part (Godovanets, 2003). There are several unverified reports of observations of «large» predators within the boundaries of the Uzhansky National Park. The work carried out by the author of this report on the identification of nests in winter with the subsequent revision of them during the nesting period together with the employees of the Uzhansky National Park was carried out in 2005–2008. The lack of a zoologist in the staff of the park and the low awareness of the inspectors, along with the specifics of the border strip, made it impossible to collect reliable information in the upper reaches of the Uzh

Golden Eagle photographed by a camera trap, 18.02.2024.
Беркут, сфотографований фотопасткою.

river basin. Cooperative studies with hunting organizations gave more reliable information in the form of photos from camera traps, which are purchased in large quantities by hunters mainly for the protection of lands. The issue of using camera traps has become especially relevant in the last 3 years. About 100 camera traps were purchased by the hunters of the Uzh river basin, the vast majority of which have the function of sending photos or videos to the specified e-mail address.

Birds are less often captured by a camera trap than large mammals. In this particular case, the camera trap was placed near the dead animal, which may have attracted the Golden Eagle. The first observation was in Lyuta river basin (48° 48' 15'' N, 22° 35' 18'' E) from February 18, 2024 (photo). Subsequently, the bird visited this place 4 more times at intervals of 3–4 days. The blue ring on the right foot was installed by Slovak colleagues (pers. com.), but the low quality of the photo did not allow us to establish the date and place of ringing. According to the information from colleague Štefan Danko (Slovakia), this is a three- to four-year-old female ringed by Slovakian ornithologists 300–500 km from the photo registration site. He suggested the possible nesting of the species in this region.

The registered photo confirms the Golden Eagle's visit to the Uzh river basin in the Transcarpathia and the probability of a nesting pair appearing in western part of this region.

REFERENCES

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